

FEMALE CATTLE BIOTECHNOLOGY EFFECTIVENESS OF ACHIEVEMENTS

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Abstract. In this article, the efficiency of obtaining female calves by insemination with female seeds of the Black-Ola cattle breed cows, which are kept on a large scale by the population of our country, is presented. The live weight of cows bred with same-sex seeds, the characteristics of seed retention, and growth indicators were studied.

Keywords: Animal husbandry, cattle, selection, fetus, breeding, biotechnology, cow, calf, artificial insemination.

Абстрактный. В данной статье представлена эффективность получения телят методом осеменения женскими семенами коров черно-ольской породы крупного рогатого скота, которых в больших масштабах содержит население нашей страны. Изучена живая масса коров, выращенных с однополыми семенами, особенности сохранности семян и показатели роста.

Ключевые слова: Животноводство, крупный рогатый скот, селекция, плод, племенная работа, биотехнология, корова, теленок, искусственное осеменение.

INTRODUCTION

It is important to ensure the needs of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for livestock products, to maintain stable food security. Demand and demand for industry products is increasing year by year. It is urgent to increase the efficiency of this sector.

In the production of high-quality feed and ecological livestock products, it is important to strengthen the feed base, to feed livestock with balanced energetic and

full-value rations, taking into account their physiological condition on a scientific basis. For this purpose, in the cultivation of quality fodder, a reasonable scientific approach should be taken from the arable land, increasing the amount of nutritious crops, timely planting of repeated and intermediate crops, hay for the winter, silage, beetroot, high-quality alfalfa hay, wheat straw and accumulation of other types of nutrients is important. It is very important to improve the breed of local breeds of cattle, to create a herd of cattle with high productivity in a short period of time.

Artificial insemination of cows mated with imported and sexed seeds is expected to result in 95-96% female calves, as well as breeding cattle with high productivity in a short period of time by improving fertility and productivity characteristics. It is possible to create a herd.

Productive cattle breeds brought to our country from abroad are considered effective in improving the breeding quality of local cattle, but it takes a lot of time and money to constantly bring cattle from abroad and adapt them to the conditions. In addition, today there are 13 million cattle in Uzbekistan, of which 4.6 million are cows. The average milk produced from each cow in the republic is 2300 kg, and 93% of the total number of cattle belongs to households. About 80% of the cows in households belong to the local breed, and their milk yield is average, 1500-1600 kg. The main reasons for the productivity of livestock are the inability of most households to fully satisfy the demand for cattle feed, the lack of knowledge in cattle feeding, care and breeding.

The live weight of the experimental cows was weighed on an electronic scale, the body dimensions were measured using a measuring tape, a compass and a leptin rod. It was found that the average live weight of dairy cows was 13 kg higher than the control group.

Yagirin's height is 2.22 cm compared to the control group. was high. The average body length of the experimental cows is 7.33 cm. high, chest circumference 1.78 cm., buttock height 3.67 cm., chest depth 4.55 cm. was found to be superior.

Chest width is 4.55 cm compared to the experimental group. was found to be higher than cows in the control group. The average ischial bone of the cows in the experimental group was 0.15 cm when we measured it with a compass. the difference was not noticeable, and the circumference of the leg was 0.6 cm. it has been.

Artificial insemination of experimental cows: Preparations were made for artificial insemination of experimental cows in the experimental farm of the Animal Husbandry and Poultry Scientific Research Institute.

When artificially inseminating experimental black-bred cows, only female calves are obtained, and the number of carcasses increases. Ultimately, it will be possible to create a herd of cattle with improved productivity in a short period of time. In cattle breeding, it is important to study the changes in their fertility indicators. The condition of keeping, the complete value of the feed ration and other reasons can be.

We continued the cows in the control group based on the technology adopted on the farm. We kept the cows in the experimental group in closed buildings during the winter. In the spring and summer seasons, conditions of protection were created, and during the hot summer days, they were kept in tall verandas blocking the sunlight above the spreading areas. The influence of the conditions of keeping the cows in the experimental group on milk productivity and its quality, as well as the effect on fertility characteristics is also being studied. In addition, the cows in the experimental groups, whose estrus is not clear, were actively exercised several times a day, and the time of sexual orientation was observed. The cows that came to the cowshed were separated and brought to special places for artificial insemination, where artificial insemination of cows was carried out.

Calving (breeding) of experimental cows: Cows were transferred to the farrowing ward 10 days before calving. They were kept in groups and under the porch of the building. Cows were fed according to the diet of dairy cows, only 10-

14 days before calving, milk-producing juicy feeds were sharply reduced from the diet.

Cows were transferred to a specially prepared room (box) 1-2 days before calving. The floor of the room was covered with straw and all necessary measures were taken. As 2 cows in the experiment were tired during pregnancy, the help of an obstetrician was provided, the rest of the cows gave birth normally. After the cows gave birth, the impurities were cleaned from her body. The external genitalia were washed and disinfected. The udder of the cow was washed with warm water (37-38 s) and the first milk was expressed in a separate container, after which the calf was suckled.

CONCLUSION

If the conditions of care, feeding and feeding of cows during the estrous period and after calving are carried out in a timely manner, the service period of cows will be shortened, they will be inseminated and fertilized in time, and their fertility will improve.

Early detection of strangulation in cattle in 28 days using the UZI device gives good results and economic efficiency is achieved.

During artificial insemination of cows, the period from 18 to 28 months of age is considered to be a high period of retention of seeds, and it was observed that this indicator is lower in older cows.

Homozygous sex cells with XX chromosomes are considered to be 4% lighter than XY chromosomal sex cells, and a 90% result can be achieved in the extraction of seeds.

Insemination with same-sex seeds will greatly help in the future breeding of calves according to the plan.

In the short term, it is possible to increase the number of female cattle and affect milk production.

In the territory of Uzbekistan, it is possible to increase the income of the population by raising a large number of black-and-white cattle adapted to care for households, and insemination with same-sex seeds.

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